

Formulation development, optimization, and evaluation of fast-dispersing tablets of cefixime trihydrate for pediatric use

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Abstract

The proposed study aimed to formulate and optimize the design of a fast-dispersing tablet (FDT) of cefixime trihydrate (dispersed in a teaspoon of water) tailored for pediatric patients (0–12 years). To assess the percentage concentration of the cefixime in the formulated tablets, the HPLC method was validated and established linearity, $r^2 = 0.9998$ in the range of 20–0.078 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The pre-formulation study was carried out. Crospovidone (X1), croscarmellose sodium (X2), and sodium starch glycolate (X3) were selected as key independent variables, and their impact was executed on friability and disintegration time as dependent variables. Central composite design (2^3) optimized the process using eight formulations (F1–F8) with different X1, X2, and X3 concentrations. F2 and F9 (additional, similar to F2) were selected as checkpoint batches (CPB) using Design Expert software. Stability studies of CPB were conducted. The study concluded that the newly formulated tablets could be optimized quickly, with their drug release and absorption profiles resembling those of the marketed suspension. Additionally, the tablets were found to be a viable alternative to the suspension.

Keywords

cefixime trihydrate, fast dispersing tablet, direct compression method, Design Expert 13, super-disintegrants, taste masking

Introduction

Antimicrobial drugs are crucial for modern medicine. The emergence and spread of drug-resistant pathogens endanger our ability to treat common infections and perform life-saving procedures like cancer chemotherapy, cesarean section, and other surgeries. In 2019, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) caused 1.27 million deaths worldwide, and it contributed to a total of 4.95 million deaths (Antimicrobial Resistance Collaborators 2022).

Infectious bacteria can be classified as Gram-positive or Gram-negative. Treatment of such infections requires medication with a broad spectrum of activity. Cephalosporins

are a type of medication that can inhibit bacterial cell wall mucopeptide synthesis and have a wide range of activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. One such medication is cefixime trihydrate ($\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_5\text{O}_{10}\text{S}_2$), which is a third-generation cephalosporin that can be taken orally (Satoskar et al. 1999; Tripathi 2003).

Many pediatric and geriatric patients do not like to take conventional tablet dosage forms because it is difficult to swallow (dysphagia) (Lindgren and Janzon 1991). which becomes a major factor affecting compliance with drug use (Cornilă et al. 2022). The development of fast-dispersing tablet (FDT) formulation could help solve the problem of patient compliance, which may arise due to solid dosage

form (dysphagia) and the disadvantages of liquid dosage form, such as uniformity of dose, handling of dosage container, and storage of medicine (stability) (Khan et al. 2022; Sharma and Leel 2022; Sindhu et al. 2023).

A study was conducted to obtain the opinions of Spanish physicians to assess factors affecting drug prescriptions with the importance given to the patient's opinion, degree of acceptance, and preference for fast-dispersing tablets (FDT). The study comprised 7,686 patients, 88% of whom agreed to switch their current antihistaminic drug to a new FDT anti-allergy drug (Reig et al. 2006).

Clinical trials investigation indicated that cefixime is better than amoxicillin and cefaclor for the treatment of acute otitis media in children two months to 13 years of age (Howie and Owen 1987; Johnson et al. 1991; Bluestone 1993; Harrison et al. 1993; Rodriguez et al. 1993), as it is effective in treating cases due to H influenzae and M catarrhalis (75 to 100% cure or improvement). One more study reported that for streptococcal pharyngitis in children 4 to 12 years of age, cefixime was better at both eradicating and preventing recurrences of streptococcus and penicillin V (Block et al. 1992). Additionally, another case study shows that cefixime is effective for the treatment of urinary tract infection when compared with trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (Dagan et al. 1992), Salmonella typhi infection (Bhutta et al. 1994), and multiresistant Shigella species gastroenteritis (Ashkenazi et al. 1993) in children.

Oral cefixime suspension is the drug of choice in the clinical setup for children (0–12 years) (CEFIXIME 2021). However, the non-uniformity and handling of the medicine sometimes cause the inappropriate delivery of dosage (Deicke and Süverkrüp 2000). If an appropriate and convenient drug delivery system is developed, better control over non-adherence can be achieved. To overcome all these demerits, an advanced delivery system is introduced in which cefixime is developed in tablet dosage form in a suitable strength to meet dose requirements with minimum excipients. Before administration, the tablet will be placed on a teaspoon along with a few drops of water to make it a palatable suspension with an accurate unit dose (Kumar and Ghosh 2019; Cirri et al. 2024).

To improve the quality of medicines, pharmaceutical companies are facing decisive issues in designing an optimized pharmaceutical formulation in a short period without a series of trials. Design Expert (DE) is a computer-based optimization technique working on response surface methodology (RSM) that helps to utilize experimental designs and operating conditions in better ways (Bouckaert et al. 1996; Huang et al. 2004).

The current study focuses on the formulation of fast-dispersing tablets of cefixime trihydrate as a novel alternative to pediatric suspensions available in the market. First, the focus of the study was to develop FDTs that require dispersion in 5 mL or less of water before administration, which made them the ideal alternative to conventional “100 mg/5 mL cefixime suspensions”. This approach addressed significant challenges associated with suspensions, such as dose inaccuracy due to improper shaking, stability issues after

reconstitution, and transportation difficulties—factors critically relevant in pediatric care, especially in resource-limited settings (EMANS 2024: Reflection Paper 2024). Secondly, the dose strength in FDTs matched the commonly prescribed pediatric suspension (100 mg/5 mL), ensuring dose equivalency and therapeutic consistency. The tablets were formulated using three super disintegrants in varying ratios, optimized through Design Expert software (version 13.0.5.0). This innovative approach with disintegration time within 30 seconds was reported in literature also (Mistry and Batchelor 2017; Patel et al. 2021). It aims to address key issues associated with pediatric suspensions, such as non-compliance due to difficulties in handling and transportation during daily activities. Additionally, the formulation tackles dosing inaccuracies common with liquid dosage forms, where household spoons of varying sizes are often used. The study focused on ensuring that the FDTs meet key pediatric requirements like rapid dispersion, dose equivalency to conventional 100 mg/5 mL cefixime suspension, rapid disintegration, and friability (NMT 1%). It also emphasized accurate volume control and taste masking, which are critical factors for pediatric patients, who often dislike the inconsistent taste of liquid medications. This study aimed to address the limitations of conventional pediatric suspensions by improving dose accuracy, ease of administration, enhanced stability, and better patient compliance. This strategy has the potential to significantly extend the lifecycle of pediatric medications and provide a cost-effective and commercially viable alternative to conventional suspensions (Hanif et al. 2019; Cornilă et al. 2022).

Scheme 1. Flow diagram—overview of the study.

Materials and methods

Materials

Cefixime trihydrate, sodium starch glycolate, sodium stearyl fumarate, sucralose, and strawberry flavor were obtained as a gift sample from Julphar (Gulf pharmaceutical industry, UAE). Mannitol, microcrystalline cellulose, crospovidone, and croscarmellose sodium were the other excipients used

in the tablet formulation. HPLC-grade reagents such as methanol and distilled water were used in the preparation of the mobile phase. Sodium dihydrogen phosphate, monobasic potassium phosphate, sodium hydroxide, orthophosphoric acid, and methylene blue are HPLC-grade reagents.

Methods

Ethical statement

The approval of the Research and Ethics Committee of RAKMHSU was obtained before the work was initiated. Research Approval # RAKMHSU-REC-158-2021/22-PG-P. Date of Approval: June 9, 2022 (Suppl material 5).

Experimental design

The logical development of drug dosage forms started with preformulation testing, which involved angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, and Hausner ratio. These parameters were used for drugs and excipients individually as well as in a combined blend of powder. These are the functional characteristics that help to evaluate the potential properties of the formulation and support to create stable and acceptable dosage forms (Desu et al. 2015).

FTIR spectroscopy (using Agilent Technologies, Cary 630 FTIR) was employed to analyze the compatibility of the pure drug and each excipient separately as well as the combined mixture of drug and excipients. Eight batches were prepared with different ratios, and the distinctive peaks for the corresponding functional group in the compound were identified. The scanning range was 500 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} .

The addition of sweeteners and flavoring agents is one of the simplest techniques used in taste masking. In this study, sucralose as a sweetener and strawberry as a flavoring agent were added to mask the taste of cefixime. In addition, mannitol was added to enhance the pleasant feeling in the mouth (to improve pediatric compliance). The spectrophotometric method was used to evaluate the taste (European Medicines Agency 2006; Sonawane et al. 2010; Sagar et al. 2012; Pawar and Joshi 2014; Kalbande et al. 2022).

In the spectrophotometric method, distilled water and phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) were used to dissolve both the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and the powder blends (formulation) separately. The filtrate was analyzed using a UV spectrophotometer at 288 nm. Different studies demonstrate that the masking of taste in vivo is likely to be successful if the reading of the powder blend is less than the threshold value of API alone.

Additionally, the in vivo sensory evaluation of cefixime trihydrate was conducted with the participation of 8 healthy volunteers. Prior to the study, all participants provided written consent by completing an informed consent form, ensuring ethical compliance.

The taste assessment was carried out using the Latin Square Method to minimize bias and randomize the order of sample presentation. A total of four taste samples were evaluated during the study.

Pre-taste sensory screening: Before initiating the taste campaign, volunteers were screened for their basic taste recognition ability using 2% sucrose for sweet taste, 0.2% sodium chloride for salty taste, 0.07% citric acid for sour taste, and 0.07% caffeine for bitter taste as standard solutions. This pre-screening ensured that all participants had normal taste perception.

Sensory evaluation procedure

Each volunteer was asked to taste the samples and rate their perception based on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Very Bad; 2 = Bad; 3 = No Taste; 4 = Good; 5 = Excellent.

Volunteers rinsed their mouths with water between samples to avoid carryover effects. The data collected were used to assess the palatability, taste-masking efficiency, and overall acceptability of the cefixime trihydrate formulations.

Quantification of drug in newly developed formulation

The preliminary concept of the quantitative analytical method was screened from the literature survey (Arshad et al. 2009; Mathew et al. 2016; Hassouna and Mahmoud 2018). A 65:35% v/v mixture of buffer (12.5 mM sodium dihydrogen phosphate) and methanol was taken as the mobile phase. The pH was adjusted at 2.75 with 85% orthophosphoric acid (Arshad et al. 2009). The mobile phase was filtered and sonicated before use. The standard stock solution was prepared by weighing 5 mg of cefixime trihydrate (reference standard), adding 1 mL of methanol, and making the volume up to 10 mL using the mobile phase. The final concentration of the standard stock solution was equivalent to $200\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$. The calibration curve was constructed using a series of dilutions such as 10, 5, 2.5, 1.25, 0.625, 0.3125, 0.15625, and $0.078\text{ }\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. Absorbance was measured at $\lambda\text{ }288\text{ nm}$ using the HPLC analytical method (SPD-20A Shimadzu UV-VIS). For the authentication and reproducibility of the method, the method was validated for the parameters that included system suitability, range and linearity, the limit of detection, the limit of quantification, accuracy, and precision.

Development and optimization of fast-dispersing tablets (FDT)

Cefixime Trihydrate (dispersing in a teaspoon) tablet was developed using a combination of different disintegrants. In this design, three super disintegrants, including croscopolidone, croscarmellose sodium, and sodium starch glycolate, were used as independent variables. Experimental trials were performed at eight (8) possible combinations. Other ingredients present in the formulation also had critical roles, like mannitol as a diluent, microcrystalline cellulose pH 102 as a binder, sodium stearyl fumarate as a lubricant, sucralose as a sweetening agent, which masked the taste of cefixime, and strawberry flavor added pleasant organoleptic properties to the formulation.

The tablet was designed with 100 mg of cefixime, which covers the complete dose range in pediatric patients. Half a tablet could deliver 50 mg, and $1\frac{1}{2}$ tablets would deliver 150 mg (range of pediatric dose: 8–10 mg/kg). The tablet's

gross weight was adjusted at 300 mg using different ratios of three independent variables and other diluents.

The direct compression method was used to prepare all eight batches of formulation with varied quantities of crospovidone, croscarmellose sodium, and sodium starch glycolate. The powder blend was compressed on 8.5 mm round plain concave-shaped punches at a theoretical weight of 300 mg \pm 7.5%. The hardness limit of the tablet was NMT 6.0 kp (between 3–6 kp), disintegration time was adjusted at less than 1 minute (Siddiqui et al. 2010), and friability at less than 1% (USP 41-NF 36).

To optimize the formulation, the effect of the concentration of crospovidone (X₁), croscarmellose sodium (X₂), and sodium starch glycolate (X₃) was assessed to evaluate the impact on disintegration time (Y₁) and friability percentage (Y₂).

The "Design Expert (DE) version 13" software was used to optimize the process and adjust the level of variables. DE was used to systematically optimize the ratios of three commonly used superdisintegrants to achieve the desired quality attributes. Factorial designs 2³ (three factors, two levels) with two (2) central points and eight runs were used. The independent variables' coding and actual values are as follows in Tables 1, 2. The composition of 8 formulations is given in Table 3.

Table 1. Coded value for independent variable.

Level	Concentration of Crospovidone X ₁	Concentration of Croscarmellose Sodium X ₂	Concentration of Sodium Starch Glycolate X ₃
-1	2%	2%	3%
1	4%	4%	6%

Table 2. 2³ factorial design layout.

Batch no.	Level of X ₁	Level of X ₂	Level of X ₃
F1	-1	-1	1
F2	-1	1	-1
F3	-1	-1	-1
F4	1	1	-1
F5	1	1	1
F6	-1	1	1
F7	1	-1	-1
F8	1	-1	1

X₁—concentration of crospovidone, X₂—concentration of croscarmellose sodium, X₃—concentration of sodium starch glycolate.

Table 3. The detail of prototype batches F1–F8.

Ingredients	Formulation Code (mg/ Tablet)							
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
*Cefixime Trihydrate	113.6	113.6	113.6	113.6	113.6	113.6	113.6	113.6
Mannitol	109.4	103.4	103.4	97.4	100.4	94.4	94.4	88.4
Microcrystalline Cellulose	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Crospovidone	6	12	6	12	6	12	6	12
Croscarmellose Sodium	6	6	12	12	6	6	12	12
Sodium Starch Glycolate	9	9	9	9	18	18	18	18
Sodium Stearyl Fumarate	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Sucralose	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Strawberry Flavor	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Total quantity in mg	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

*113.6 mg cefixime trihydrate is equivalent to 100 mg cefixime.

Evaluation of quality attributes

Measurement of pharmaceutical parameters helps to ensure that the tablet contains the proper amount of the drug. To design and construct the desirable tablets, quality control analysis is essential. Appearance, weight variation, thickness, dissolution test, assay of the tablet, hardness, friability, disintegration, and wetting time were carried out to establish the quality of formulated dispersible tablets.

All tablets looked good and elegant without any deformity, along with adequate consistency in weight, size, hardness, and overall appearance. 20 tablets were individually weighed to perform the weight variation test. The average tablet weight was then calculated, and the weight of each tablet was compared to the average. According to USP, the percentage deviation was \pm 7.5% (USP 41 and NF 36), and all the tablets were within the limits. A strong relationship was seen between hardness and thickness, where hardness controlled the thickness. In general, the thickness should be within the \pm 5% variation (USP 41 and NF 36). Veego friabilator was used to assess friability at 25 rpm for up to 4 minutes. For the majority of cases, mean weight loss was not more than 1.0% (n = 3 samples) (USP 41 and NF 36). The wetting test was performed on the tablets by placing each tablet on the surface of 1.25 mL of 0.1% methylene blue solution in a petri dish. The time taken for complete wetting of the tablet was recorded. This procedure was individually conducted for all eight batches (Park et al. 2008).

According to USP 41 and NF 36, the disintegration test was performed in a basket assembled in water as a medium maintained at 37 \pm 2 °C. In each of the 6 tubes, one tablet was placed, and the time for the disintegration of the tablet was recorded. In the present study, as per USP 41-NF 36, dissolution apparatus II was used for the in vitro dissolution test. The buffer solution was prepared by weighing 6.8 g/L of monobasic potassium phosphate and dissolving it in water. pH was adjusted to 7.2 with 1N sodium hydroxide and maintained at 37 \pm 0.5 °C. Transferred 900 mL of buffer in six vessels of the dissolution apparatus. In each vessel, one tablet was placed, and the speed of the paddle was adjusted to 50 rpm.

Five milliliters (5 mL) of samples were withdrawn from each vessel at various intervals of time, such as 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, and 60 minutes, and measured absorbance at 288 nm. A standard working solution was prepared using 5 mg of cefixime trihydrate (reference standard) powder and diluted to obtain a concentration of 500 µg/mL in the mobile phase. The final concentration of the working solution was 100 µg/mL.

The drug content assay was evaluated using a sample solution that was prepared by weighing five formulated tablets of cefixime, and the average weight of the tablets was calculated. The amount of powder equivalent to 100 mg of cefixime was weighed and dissolved in methanol and then the volume was made up with mobile phase. The final concentration of the solution was 100 µg/mL and measured at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 288$ nm using HPLC.

Optimization of checkpoint batch (CPB)

The novelty of the study lies in the systematic optimization of the combination and ratio adjustment of three super disintegrants using Design Expert software. This approach was specifically tailored to meet pediatric formulation requirements, ensuring disintegration within 30 seconds, dispersion in ≤ 5 mL of water, and dose equivalency to the conventional 100 mg/5 mL suspension.

In the current study, after feeding the disintegration time and friability percentage data into the Design Expert software, the program generated eight different formulation runs. Among these, the formulation F2 ensured the desired results in terms of both disintegration time and friability. Additionally, one more formulation was found to have the same composition and performance characteristics as F2.

Therefore, two checkpoint batches were prepared: the F2 formulation and another batch (F9) replicating the composition that matched F2. These checkpoint batches served to validate and confirm the reproducibility and consistency of the formulation's performance. The required results were achieved in subsequent batches, developing the sense of robustness of the formulation process. CPB-F2 and F9 were assessed with a target of less than 30 seconds of disintegration time and less than 1 % friability. Both the CPBs were kept for stability studies and evaluated for their quality attributes (Table 4).

Table 4. Checkpoint batches—F2 and F9.

Name of Material	Batch Size: 100 Tablets	
	F2 mg/tablet	F9 mg/tablet
Cefixime Trihydrate	113.6	113.6
Mannitol	103.4	101
Microcrystalline Cellulose	40	40
Crospovidone	12	12
Croscarmellose Sodium	6	8.4
Sodium Starch Glycolate	9	9
Sodium Stearyl Fumarate	6	6
Sucralose	5	5
Strawberry Flavor	5	5
Total	300.0 mg	300.0 mg

Stability studies

The tablets of CPBs were packed in Alu/Alu blister packing as well as in an amber-colored bottle and subjected to stability studies where quality attributes of the prepared tablets were evaluated. The tablets were stored at an accelerated temperature, i.e., 40 ± 2 °C, and relative humidity of $75 \pm 5\%$ R.H. (European Medicines Agency 2003) for 3 months at intervals of 0, 1, 2, and 3 months as per the recommendation of the ICH guideline.

Results

Construction of calibration curve and validation

In the present study, the HPLC method was modified and validated as per feasibility. The regression factor (r^2) of 0.9998 shows the linear relationship between the peak areas and concentration in the range of 20 to 0.078 µg/mL (Figs 1, 2). Whereas, the retention time of the peak was 10 min. The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantitation (LOQ) were found to be 0.00069 and 0.00211 µg/mL, respectively. The system suitability was estimated by injecting six samples of the same concentration (100 µg/mL) of cefixime trihydrate with RSD of retention times and peak areas of 0.872 and 0.7776, respectively. The theoretical plate and tailing factor of the system suitability were also calculated, which were found to be 3904.6385 and 0.878, respectively. The accuracy of the method was carried out on three levels of concentration, i.e., 50, 100, and 150%, with a recovery percentage of 98%–102%. There was no significant variation in area under the curve for the three concentrations with RSD 0.286, 0.708, and 0.428 for intra-day variability. Similarly, no significant variation was observed in the inter-day variation.

Experimental design

Preformulation studies are one of the challenging areas in designing and developing prototype formulations (European Medicines Agency 2013). Thereby, helping to screen out the appropriate excipients to construct a desired formulation.

Drug-excipient compatibility studies were conducted using FTIR. Cefixime trihydrate pure drug shows the bond vibrations at 3526 cm^{-1} (-NH stretching), 3223 cm^{-1} (OH stretching), 3132 cm^{-1} (aromatic C-H stretching), 2888 cm^{-1} (aliphatic C-H stretching), and 1766 cm^{-1} (C = O stretching), 1665 cm^{-1} (C = N stretching), and 1588 cm^{-1} (C = C stretching). The peaks of NH stretching, OH stretching, and C = O stretching are intact in all the formulations (Fig. 3).

Estimation of pharmaceutical parameters was carried out to verify that the newly constructed tablets were as per the specifications of the designed study (Table 7).

Figure 1. Calibration curve (linearity) of cefixime.

Figure 2. Chromatograms of cefixime samples at 288 nm. A. Highest conc. 20 µg/mL; B. Lowest conc. 0.078 µg/mL.

Figure 3. FTIR spectra for cefixime Ref. and formulation Blend—F2.

Optimization of checkpoint batch (CPB)

Design Expert software was employed to optimize the formulation design. Three independent variables were selected to evaluate their influence on the dependent responses, particularly disintegration time and friability. A 2^3 full factorial design was employed to model the data,

enhancing statistical process control and optimizing surface responses, resulting in a total of 8 experimental runs.

Stability studies

It is one of the crucial steps in determining the validity of the formulation. It helps to provide the pathway of drug

decomposition, which helps to manage the final product in the concluding container (Table 11). Pharmaceutical parameters were evaluated for CPBs.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to develop and optimize fast-dispersing tablets (FDTs) of cefixime trihydrate specifically designed for pediatric patients aged 0–12 years. The goal was to create a formulation that ensures dose equivalency to the conventional 100 mg/5 mL cefixime suspension, rapid dispersion in 5 mL or less of water, disintegration time of less than 30 seconds, and friability below 1% for mechanical robustness.

This study aimed to address the limitations of conventional pediatric suspensions, such as dosing inaccuracies, stability issues, and storage concerns, by developing a solid oral dosage form that offers improved ease of administration, enhanced stability, and better patient compliance.

To assess the newly formulated tablets accurately, a precise analytical method is required that meets all the acceptance criteria and is fit for purpose. It is capable of reliably and accurately quantifying the active pharmaceutical ingredient in the sample. Initially, the standard characteristics of different excipients were evaluated for their physicochemical properties. The basic concept of the selection of excipients was picked from the marketed brands of cefixime (suspension and tablets). The preliminary study of the excipients helps to understand their roles and interactions with the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API).

The present study is focused on the construction of FDT that can be easily dispersed in a few ml of water in a teaspoon to improve the acceptance of medication in kids. The reason behind the selection of crospovidone, croscarmellose sodium, and sodium starch glycolate is to improve the mechanism of swelling, wicking, or deformation in the tablets. The literature study shows that increasing the concentration of all these three disintegrants exhibited faster disintegration of the tablet (Abha and Kaur 2015; Antari et al. 2021; Manzoor 2021) (Table 5).

After the initial studies of excipients (Table 6), the blends of powder were prepared as per the study design to construct the basic structure of the FDT formulation and evaluated for their bulk, tapped density, Carr's index, and angle of repose (Table 6), which measure the powder blends if they have suitable flow and compression properties. These parameters help in predicting and controlling the behavior of the powder, which affects the quality and desirability of the final product.

Carr's Index (CI) of cefixime alone was 20%, but after blending with excipients, it ranged from 17.39 to 24.39%, providing a quantitative measure of the powder's flowability (Table 5). Therefore, the CI of all formulation blends (F1–F8) indicated that they persist in moderate flow (less than 15% = excellent; greater than 25% = poor flow). Whereas the angle of repose of all formulations falls in the range of 24–30° (less than 30° = good flowability; greater than 40° = poor flow), it helps to control the feeding and filling processes during tablet compression (Table 8).

In the proposed study, the compatibility of the excipients with each other and with the active pharmaceutical

Table 5. Preformulation studies of active and excipients.

Formulation Materials	Bulk density (g/mL)	Tapped density (g/mL)	Carr's Index %	Hausner's Ratio*	Angle of Repose* θ
Cefixime Trihydrate	0.6	0.75	20	1.25	-
Mannitol	0.38	0.66	42.85	1.75	35
Microcrystalline Cellulose	0.31	0.45	31.24	1.45	35
Crospovidone (C)	0.26	0.35	26.32	1.35	39
Croscarmellose sodium (CS)	0.41	0.55	25	1.33	44
Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG)	0.5	0.71	29.99	1.42	43
Sodium Stearyl Fumarate	0.26	0.4	34.8	1.53	43
Sucralose	0.3	0.5454	44.99	1.818	19

*(Based on Mean \pm SD; n = 3).

Table 6. Flow properties of the powder blends.

Formulation Code	Bulk density (g/cc)	Tapped density (g/cc)	Flow properties*		
			Carr's index %	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose * θ
F1	0.38	0.46	17.39	1.21	24
F2	0.35	0.46	23.91	1.31	30
F3	0.34	0.42	19.04	1.23	28
F4	0.34	0.42	19.04	1.23	30
F5	0.32	0.42	23.8	1.31	28
F6	0.31	0.41	24.39	1.32	25
F7	0.32	0.42	23.8	1.31	25
F8	0.32	0.42	23.8	1.31	24

*Angle of repose = Excellent: range 25–30.

*Flow character = Excellent: Compressibility index = \leq 10; Hausner ratio = 1.00–1.11.

Table 7. Estimation of pharmaceutical parameters of F1–F8.

Formulation Code	Weight variation (mg)	Diameter (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (Kp)	Friability (%)	Wetting time (Sec)	Disintegration time (Sec)	Content Assay
F1	300.96 ± 1.99	8.44 ± 0.05	3.745 ± 0.04	4.75 ± 0.26	0.71	53.3 ± 2.34	152.4 ± 0.83	102 ± 0.48
F2	303.08 ± 1.19	8.46 ± 0.08	4.0 ± 0.0	4.05 ± 0.49	1.02	45.4 ± 1.13	15.8 ± 2.66	102.89 ± 0.45
F3	303.69 ± 1.26	8.42 ± 0.04	3.76 ± 0.06	4.75 ± 0.26	0.73	100.6 ± 0.96	85.6 ± 0.6	100.96 ± 0.13
F4	302.72 ± 1.43	8.47 ± 0.04	4.02 ± 0.04	3.93 ± 0.38	1.06	17.2 ± 3.67	20.3 ± 2.37	101.12 ± 0.54
F5	302.42 ± 2.05	8.38 ± 0.03	3.745 ± 0.04	4.4 ± 0.39	0.24	153.8 ± 1.95	187.7 ± 0.43	98.9 ± 0.53
F6	302.56 ± 1.6	8.385 ± 0.02	3.87 ± 0.04	4.3 ± 0.25	0.19	76.7 ± 2.38	62.6 ± 0.82	94.9 ± 0.76
F7	303.13 ± 1.97	8.37 ± 0.03	3.765 ± 0.04	4.5 ± 0.4	0.13	151.2 ± 2.51	192.3 ± 0.42	99.98 ± 0.58
F8	303.49 ± 1.99	8.405 ± 0.03	3.835 ± 0.05	3.9 ± 0.1	0.29	104.8 ± 3.5	66.3 ± 0.72	95.64 ± 0.51

Table 8. ANOVA and regression analysis for the disintegration time.

Parameter	Sum of squares (SS)	Degree of freedom (df)	Mean square (MS)	F value	p-value Prob > F	R ²
Model	5.90	3	1.97	46.84	0.0014 significant	0.9723
A-Crospovidone	4.06	1	4.06	96.73	0.0006	-
C-Sodium Starch Glycolate	1.59	1	1.59	37.82	0.0035	-
AC	0.2503	1	0.2503	5.96	0.0711	-
Residual	0.1680	4	0.0420	-	-	-

ingredient (cefixime trihydrate) was evaluated using FTIR, a well-established and reliable method in pharmaceutical formulation development. The FTIR spectra of cefixime trihydrate showed no significant shifting or loss of key functional peaks, indicating the structural integrity of the drug. Similarly, in the drug-excipient mixtures, the principal peaks of cefixime trihydrate remained unchanged, suggesting no interaction or interference with the functional groups (Fig. 3). This confirms that the excipients and active drugs are chemically compatible, ensuring the stability, efficacy, and optimal performance of the final pharmaceutical formulation.

After confirmation of the suitability and compatibility of formulation blends, FDT was formulated by the direct compression method using different concentrations of independent variables, which were calculated by applying 2³ factorial designs (DE vs. 13) and preparing eight different batches of tablets.

The originality of this study is based on the optimization of the ratio of three superdisintegrants (crospovidone, croscarmellose sodium, and sodium starch glycolate) to personalize medicine for pediatric patients. Unlike previous studies, this work focused on precise excipient ratio optimization to enhance both mechanical and functional tablet properties for pediatric compliance (Bee and Balasubramaniam 2009; Rojas et al. 2012; Subramanian et al. 2013; Kumar et al. 2014; Mahendrakumar et al. 2014; Hayder et al. 2015; Remya et al. 2019; Yousaf et al. 2019; Sriranga et al. 2023).

Physical quality attributes of newly formulated tablets were assessed to ensure that the tablets were as per the proposed design, such as round and pale yellow, with the standard deviation of weight variation within the acceptance limit (7.5%). The diameter and thickness of the tablet were in the range of 8 mm and 3–4 mm, respectively, as well as the hardness of the tablets was in the range of 3–4 kp, as per study specifications.

Whereas the dependent variable, the friability of most of the formulated tablets, was within 1%, and the

disintegration time was observed between 15.8 and 192.3 sec (Table 7). CPB - F2 was selected based on their least disintegration time among the 8 batches. The release of cefixime from the tablets (F2 and F4) was 85% within 5 minutes, indicating the fast dissolution subsequently gives fast bioavailability (Fig. 4). Wetting time represented the inner structure and hydrophilicity of the excipients (Pawar et al. 2011). It is related to the contact angle; the lower the wetting time, the quicker the disintegration of the tablets. In the current study, three super disintegrants were used that helped reduce not only the wetting time but also produced a good impact on the disintegration time of tablets (Gharti et al. 2015).

The proposed study focused on the acceptance of FDT among children, so taste masking was one of the challenging parameters for the development of this FDT. Therefore, sucralose and strawberry were selected to mask the intensity of the bitter taste of API (cefixime). The in vitro spectrophotometric method was used to estimate the taste of the drug. It was found that cefixime had a value of 0.978 before adding the masking agent, while the formulation blends (F1–F8) showed 0.883 ± 0.034. It was confirmed by literature that if the formulation blends value is less than the threshold value, the taste masking of the cefixime is confirmed in vivo (Sonawane et al. 2010; Sagar et al. 2012; Harsha et al. 2014; Kalbande et al. 2022).

The texture and mouthfeel of the sample prior to taste masking were reported as gritty, whereas post-taste masking, the sample exhibited a smoother, thinner consistency. Regarding taste perception, approximately 62.5 % of volunteers (5 out of 8) described the unmasked sample as sour, while 37.5 % (3 out of 8) perceived it as bitter. Additionally, 87.5% of volunteers (7 out of 8) expressed a dislike for the taste after 40 seconds of contact with the tongue, whereas only 12.5% (1 out of 8) reported disliking the taste after 20 seconds. The aftertaste was predominantly described as irritating, with volunteers noting an absence of any distinct flavor or aroma in the unmodified sample.

Figure 4. Graphical presentation of dissolution data of optimization batches.

Following the incorporation of taste-masking agents, the texture and mouthfeel were perceived as thin and smooth upon placement on the tongue. Remarkably, 100% of the volunteers (8 out of 8) described the taste-masked sample as sweet. In terms of acceptance, 87.5% (7 out of 8) of the participants liked the taste immediately upon contact with the tongue (0 seconds), while 12.5% (1 out of 8) reported liking the taste after 10 seconds of exposure. The aftertaste of the modified sample remained pleasantly sweet, and all volunteers expressed a positive response towards the taste, flavor, and aroma of the taste-masked formulation after 20 seconds.

Finally, the results of prototype formulation parameters were put in the software “Design Expert vs. 13”; regression analysis and ANOVA were calculated. Based on these calculations, the optimized amount of ingredients was calculated, and a check-point batch (CPB) was manufactured. It is also confirmed by the FDS graph (on SP value) that the data of the disintegration and friability were near 95% and the standard error mean is 72% (Fig. 5). The 3D surface plot of the standard error also confirmed the optimization batches (CPB) in Fig. 6A, B (Suppl. material 1).

The disintegration time and the concentration of the independent variables established a sufficient linear relationship, i.e., R^2 is 0.9723. The fit statistics give a predicted R^2 of 0.8893, which is in reasonable agreement with the adjusted R^2 of 0.9516, where the difference is less than 0.2.

Adeq precision measures the signal-to-noise ratio. A ratio of 15.985 indicated an adequate signal, as a ratio greater than 4 was desirable. This model can be used to navigate the design space. Here, A is crospovidone, B is croscarmellose sodium, and C is sodium starch glycolate. In addition, p-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case, A and C are significant model terms (Table 8). Variable A imparts a negative effect, while C and AC showed a positive effect on disintegration time. Crospovidone gives a value of -1.425, which implies it will inhibit or slow down the disintegration process, and it contributes around 66.94%. Whereas sodium starch glycolate and term AC show a value of 0.891 (contributes 26.17%) and 0.353 (contributes 4.12%), which indicates these two independent variables increase the process of disintegration in the formulated tablet (Suppl. material 1).

On the other hand, the regression factor for friability was 0.9881, indicating an excellent correlation between friability and the concentration of independent variables (Table 9). The predicted R^2 of 0.9522 is in reasonable agreement with the adjusted R^2 of 0.9791 with a difference of less than 0.2. Adeq precision is 22.0302, which indicated an adequate signal as the ratio was greater than 4, showing desirability. This model can be used to navigate the design space. The variables C and AC cause a negative effect on friability, whereas A has a positive effect. A, C, and AC are significant model terms as p-values are less

Figure 5. Fraction of design space.

Figure 6. A, B. 3D Surface plot of the standard error of the design of optimization batches.

Table 9. ANOVA and regression analysis for friability.

Parameter	Sum of squares (SS)	Degree of freedom (df)	Mean square (MS)	F value	p-value Prob > F	R ²
Model	0.9965	3	0.3322	110.27	0.0003 significant	0.9881
A-Crospovidone	0.0703	1	0.0703	23.34	0.0085	-
C-Sodium Starch Glycolate	0.8911	1	0.8911	295.80	< 0.0001	-
AC	0.0351	1	0.0351	11.66	0.0269	-
Residual	0.0121	4	0.0030	-	-	-

than 0.0500. Sodium starch glycolate and term AC are the two independent variables that decrease the friability or do not promote easy breaking of the tablet by values of -0.668 (contributes 88.36%) and -0.133 (contributes 3.48%). While crospovidone increases the friability by 0.188, which contributes about 6.97%.

Additionally, the data of the disintegration time and % friability were added into the software to obtain a desirability that was equal to 1. These runs disclosed one additional composition of formulation (F9), which revealed similar characteristics with high desirability (Fig. 7A, B). However, two CPBs (F2 and F9) were prepared for further evaluation and verification of the study design (Suppl. material 1).

The formulation study utilized a combination of three independent variables, such as X1 (crospovidone), X2 (croscarmellose sodium), and X3 (sodium starch glycolate), with specific ratios in formulations F2 (12:6:9) and F9 (12:8.4:9). These combinations were designed to assess their influence on key response factors—disintegration time and % friability—to identify the best-optimized prototype batches (Fig. 7A, B). To verify the accuracy of the

formulation's composition and its impact on performance, regression analysis and ANOVA were performed on the disintegration time and friability of the checkpoint batches, confirming the robustness and validity of the experimental design.

CPBs were evaluated for their pharmaceutical attributes. The average weight with \pm SD of F2 = 298.54 \pm 1.45 mg and F9 = 299.88 \pm 0.85 mg, respectively. The hardness of the tablet was found in the range of 4.3–5 Kp with \pm SD = 0.25. Friability of F2 was 0.5715 and F9 was 0.4915%. Content assays of F2 and F9 tablets were found to be 102.46% and 97.57%, respectively. These results confirmed the uniform mixing of powders. The disintegration test was found in the range of 18–19 seconds and 27–28 seconds with SD \pm 0.5477 to \pm 0.5163 for F2 and F9, respectively. These values are very closely related to the values that were obtained from the Design Expert 13.0.5.0, verifying the optimization of the desired formulation where ANOVA was conducted for the disintegration test at the 0.05 < p < 0.10 level, and the result is significant at p < 0.05 (Table 10), (Suppl. material 1).

Figure 7. A. Overlay plot for desirability; B. Overlay plot of AB.

Table 10. ANOVA—one way for disintegration of tablets.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F value	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	234.083	1	234.0833	826.1765	6.05E-11	4.964603
Within Groups	2.834	10	0.283333			
Total	236.917	11				

F-test [$P(F \leq f) = 0.45$; F Critical = 5.050].

SS - Sum of squares, df - Degree of freedom, MS - Mean square.

The releasing pattern of drugs from their tablets (F2 and F9) revealed that the tablets fulfilled the protocol of FDT. The tablets dissolved more than 85% after the completion of 5 minutes, and 100% release was observed after 10 minutes.

The value of pharmaceutical products is influenced by their safety, efficacy, and effectiveness over their entire shelf life, which can be assessed by the stability studies during the development of new formulations.

The CPBs were subjected to accelerated temperature and humidity conditions to predict long-term stability in a shorter period. During the 3 months of stability studies, weight variation, diameter, thickness, and hardness were analyzed periodically and were seen within the limits (Table 11). No significant variation was observed in the tablets packed in Alu/Alu (blister) and bottle. It was observed that the drug content and the dissolution profile of both CPBs, after three months of accelerated temperature, were the same as that at zero time (initial) of manufacturing (Fig. 8). Hence, results demonstrated that the newly designed cefixime FDT can be dispensed in a blister and a bottle. There was no significant variation observed in both packagings. Thus, Alu/Alu blisters are preferred over bottle packing to make it more patient-friendly and to avoid tampering and breakage of the container during handling and transportation.

Figure 8. Graphical presentation of cumulative % drug release (CPB-F2 and F9).**Table 11.** Stability studies of optimized prototype formulation (CPB-F2 and F9).

Time Duration	Formulation	Bottle				Blister		
		Initial	1 st month	2 nd month	3 rd month	1 st month	2 nd month	3 rd month
Physical appearance	F2 and F9	No changes	No changes	No changes	No changes	No changes	No changes	No changes
Weight variation (mg)	F2	299.88 ± 0.28	295.79 ± 0.72	298.25 ± 0.53	297.45 ± 0.14	299.86 ± 0.59	295.73 ± 0.33	298.22 ± 0.82
	F9	299.88 ± 0.28	300.96 ± 0.16	298.1 ± 0.38	298.63 ± 0.31	300.95 ± 0.22	298.34 ± 0.65	298.64 ± 0.29
Diameter (mm)	F2	8.41 ± 0.47	8.375 ± 0.23	8.45 ± 0.47	8.52 ± 0.23	8.40 ± 0.46	8.38 ± 0.23	8.41 ± 0.23
	F9	8.38 ± 0.83	8.46 ± 0.59	8.45 ± 0.59	8.475 ± 0.23	8.45 ± 0.57	8.43 ± 0.57	8.48 ± 0.46
Thickness (mm)	F2	3.68 ± 1.08	3.64 ± 1.37	3.79 ± 1.58	3.84 ± 1.3	3.69 ± 0.95	3.66 ± 0.93	3.75 ± 0.69
	F9	3.6 ± 1.67	3.75 ± 1.33	3.775 ± 0.52	3.825 ± 0.52	3.74 ± 1.42	3.75 ± 0.45	3.83 ± 0.45
Hardness (kp)	F2	4.3 ± 1.81	4.91 ± 1.62	3.95 ± 1.26	3.05 ± 1.63	4.88 ± 1.75	3.9 ± 1.75	3.09 ± 1.52
	F9	4.75 ± 1.4	4.53 ± 1.62	4.05 ± 1.23	4.05 ± 1.23	4.76 ± 1.75	4.66 ± 1.32	4.09 ± 1.75
Wetting time (Sec)	F2	24.34 ± 1.09	9.33 ± 0.51	9.16 ± 0.4	9.5 ± 0.54	9.42 ± 0.54	9.12 ± 0.51	9.47 ± 0.51
	F9	32.5 ± 1.66	6.33 ± 0.51	6.16 ± 0.4	6.5 ± 0.54	6.36 ± 0.51	6.12 ± 0.51	6.6 ± 0.54
Friability %	F2	0.5712 ± 0.85	0.6 ± 0.16	0.84 ± 0.35	0.84 ± 0.47	0.63 ± 0.16	0.81 ± 0.2	0.85 ± 0.2
	F9	0.4915 ± 0.63	0.64 ± 0.78	0.57 ± 0.35	0.83 ± 0.48	0.66 ± 0.19	0.59 ± 0.26	0.85 ± 0.27
Disintegration time (Sec)	F2	18.5 ± 1.91	24.16 ± 1.65	20.34 ± 1.5	20.67 ± 1.46	24.18 ± 1.93	20.17 ± 1.47	20.84 ± 1.89
	F9	27.34 ± 1.86	25.84 ± 1.5	19.34 ± 1.63	20.16 ± 1.98	25.82 ± 1.06	19.57 ± 1.36	20.54 ± 1.55
Drug Assay (%)	F2	102.46 ± 0.36	101.82 ± 0.61	102.05 ± 0.56	101.88 ± 0.47	101.88 ± 0.56	102.07 ± 0.65	101.69 ± 0.7
	F9	97.57 ± 0.55	98.18 ± 0.42	98.03 ± 0.56	98.2 ± 0.42	97.99 ± 0.63	98.27 ± 0.72	97.99 ± 0.6

Conclusion

The results of the study concluded that the Design of Experiments approach could help to create a formulation that ensures rapid dispersion of a tablet in 5 mL of water, provides dose equivalency to the conventional 100 mg/5 mL cefixime suspension, reduces disintegration time of tablets to less than 30 seconds, and controls the loss of mechanical strength of tablets (NMT 1%). It was also concluded that the optimization of the ratio of three commonly used superdisintegrants (crospovidone, croscarmellose sodium, and sodium starch glycolate) using a systematic approach (Design Expert) to achieve fast-dispersing tablets specifically tailored for pediatric patients addressed key challenges to meet specific pediatric formulation goals. At the same time, it reduces the fear of dysphagia that usually happens in children and geriatric patients. It is also concluded that this dosage form provides portability and a quick onset of action, as well as develops a high rate of acceptance and adherence in the patients. Additionally, the FD tablets for cefixime are not available in the markets in the UAE. Thus, these CPBs could serve as a critical milestone in the journey of FDT from their initial formulation concept to commercial production. However, it can be anticipated that shortly the importance of this FD drug delivery system will increase as compared to conventional drug delivery systems.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

Christine Philip: Investigation, Software, Validation, Writing -original draft. Shahnaz Usman: Visualization, Supervision, Writing -review & editing, Project administration. Muhammad Akram: Conceptualization, Methodology. Quamrul Islam: Resources, Data Curation.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary information

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Data type: docx

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Supplementary material 2

Informed Consent Form

Author: Christine Philip

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Supplementary material 3

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Supplementary material 4

CA

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Supplementary material 5

Official research approval letter

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